

Collection Policy for SND CARE

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SND CARE is SND's repository for research data. The repository provides a central function for making research data available and ensuring long-term access to them, with the aim of promoting transparency, reproducibility, and reuse. SND CARE is certified by the CoreTrustSeal,¹ which means that its workflows and technical solutions are defined and quality-assured in accordance with international requirements for so-called Trustworthy Data Repositories.

This document describes the principles governing which data can be managed by SND CARE. Its purpose is to ensure that data received by SND CARE can be made accessible and reused, both now and in the future, and that legal and ethical requirements are met.

This policy was adopted by SND's Steering Committee on 22 November 2021 and revised in 2026.

1. Data managed by SND CARE must constitute research data according to the following definition:

Research data are representations of phenomena that, on the basis of scientific principles, are deemed suitable for use in scientific or scholarly analysis, or for otherwise providing the basis for, or validating, research results. They have been compiled, collected, created, or otherwise generated as part of the research process.²

Data that have not been generated as part of a research process, but which are deemed suitable for providing a basis for research, may also be managed by SND CARE.

2. SND CARE accepts data, together with associated documentation and metadata, from all scientific disciplines.
3. Data must not contain information that it would be unlawful to disseminate or make available, or whose availability would conflict with existing agreements. The organization responsible for the data, that is, the principal responsible for the research, is responsible for ensuring that the data may be made available and that they are managed correctly in accordance with legal and ethical requirements.
4. Use of SND CARE is governed by the Service agreement on storage and dissemination of research data.³ The agreement is signed either at organizational level or for individual datasets. Where necessary, the service agreement must be supplemented by a data processing agreement.

¹ <https://snd.se/sites/default/files/page/2028-03-19-SNDCARE-CoreTrustSealRequirements2023-2025-1.pdf>

² What we mean by research data (2026). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18801001>

³ Service Agreement on Storage and Dissemination of Research Data / Uppdragsavtal avseende lagring och förmedling av forskningsdata (2024). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11277529>

5. Data must have a connection to Swedish higher education institutions, research-performing public authorities, or research infrastructures. Exceptions may be made following assessment and depending on available resources, such as storage capacity.
6. Data must be documented in such a way that they can be understood and reused, in accordance with SND's requirements and recommendations for data and metadata described and shared via DORIS.⁴ All submitted datasets are reviewed, and supplementary information may be required before publication.
7. SND CARE reserves the right not to accept data under the following conditions:
 - the data do not meet the criteria set out in SND's Collection Policy;
 - the data cannot be described in a manner that fulfils SND's requirements and recommendations for data and metadata;
 - conditions for data reuse and availability are not consistent with SND's mission and commitments under applicable legislation;
 - the data and related materials are of such a nature or volume that processing them is difficult or impossible given the resources and capacity available at SND CARE.

⁴ Requirements and Recommendations for Data and Metadata Described and Shared through DORIS (2025). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17964893>